

Ethnographic Insights into AI Pedagogy for Higher Education: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

This chapter presents findings from four months of ethnographic fieldwork in an experimental arts capstone unit on AI at Macquarie University (2024). Guided by the research question, “*How does the intentional design of AI learning ‘laboratories’ transform students’ AI-specific ‘habitus’ while demonstrating possibilities for sector-wide change in higher education?*” this study employs the concept of habitus of technology (Mercer 2022; Bourdieu 1977) as interpretative framework to examine how the seminar facilitated a shift from students’ initial misconceptions and mixed perceptions about AI toward technical proficiency and critical AI literacy; the capacity to move from passive to informed users who can evaluate AI capabilities and limitations, reflect on ethical implications across diverse contexts, and make deliberate choices about when and how to engage with AI tools.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI Challenge In Higher Education

Initially met with prohibitions and sanctions, institutional responses are now shifting as universities seek to integrate AI in ways that enhance rather than erode education. The most comprehensive global survey on student attitudes toward AI to date highlights troubling patterns: while 83% of students regularly use AI in their studies, only half report engaging critically with AI tools and their output, with the remaining half admitting to complacent or inappropriate use (Gillespie et al. 2025, p.92). More than 50% have concealed their use of AI to complete coursework, and 45% report presenting AI-generated content as their own. Levels of student dependence are equally concerning: 53% feel unable to complete their work without AI assistance, and nearly two-thirds (60%) report putting less effort into their studies and assessments knowing they can rely on these tools (Gillespie et al. 2025, p.92). Impacts of AI on education are mixed: while most students report benefits in increasing efficiency, work quality, creativity, and innovation, they also cite declines in critical thinking, trust, and collaboration with teachers and peers. (Gillespie et al. 2025, p.94). These figures are symptomatic of deeper issues long present in higher education: declining student engagement, credentialism, and the hollowing out of meaningful learning (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025). As algorithms become increasingly capable of completing assessments with greater sophistication and at lower costs, students—already socialised into transactional models of education and often burdened by systemic pressures—are further incentivised to outsource critical thinking to machines (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025). In light of this shifting sociotechnical landscape, leaders are now calling for a reimagining of tertiary education, urging institutions to treat AI's advance as an opportunity for sector-wide change that reorients curricula around processes rather than outcomes (Liu and Bates 2025; Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025). Still, student reporting suggests universities are lagging in setting realistic guidelines for AI use and preparing students to engage with it meaningfully in their studies and future careers (Gillespie et al. 2025, p.94).

1.2 Why Culture Matters For AI Pedagogy

Amid emerging scholarship that approaches AI pedagogy as a culturally situated process (Liu and Bates 2025; Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025), this chapter argues for the centrality of culture in shaping both the risks and possibilities of AI integration in higher education. Drawing on four months of ethnographic fieldwork in an experimental arts capstone unit on AI at Macquarie University, the chapter develops three interrelated arguments: 1) within a cultural landscape shaped by transactional models of education, systemic pressures, and rapidly advancing AI, student disengagement, performative critical thinking, and complacent reliance on AI emerge as logical consequences of a broader culture that fosters them. 2) Within this broader institutional culture, the seminar

under study was intentionally designed as a unique classroom microculture; an AI 'laboratory' whose pedagogical practices prioritised collaborative experimentation and productive failure over traditional top-down teaching methods that re-engaged students as investigators. 3) The seminar's laboratory-like pedagogy facilitated profound transformations in students' AI-specific habitus—shifts extending far beyond technical proficiency to include the development of an ethical AI awareness, transition from external to internal AI locus-of-control, and reclaimed epistemic agency that endured beyond the classroom, enabling students to derive authentic value from learning by gaining capabilities relevant to real-world contexts. Together, these findings reveal an opportunity for universities to leverage culture as a critical factor in successful AI integration. The seminar stands as evidence that intentionally designed learning environments — collaborative, exploratory, and psychologically safe — can foster productive, responsible and transparent student engagement with AI. By grounding Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025 four-pillar pedagogy in lived student experiences, this chapter provides qualitative evidence for bottom-up curricular change that supports the shift toward post-transactional educational models.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Habitus Of Technology: Bourdieu Revisited

This section outlines the concept of *habitus of technology* as an analytical lens for interpreting ethnographic findings. Drawing on Bourdieu's classic formulation and contemporary adaptations (Mercer 2022; Romele and Rodighiero 2020; Sayer 2005), this framework illuminates both the micro-level transformations observed among students and the macro-level institutional inertia hindering AI integration in higher education.

Bourdieu's (1977) concept of habitus refers to 'systems of durable, transposable dispositions, structured structures predisposed to function as structuring structures' (Bourdieu 1977, p.72). In simpler terms, habitus is a set of ingrained dispositions—habits, perceptions, and tendencies—that guide how individuals perceive and act in the world. It is shaped by social structures ('structured structure') while simultaneously shaping cultural practices and social life ('structuring structure'). As such, habitus operates as an unconscious framework through which social structures are internalised and reproduced in everyday thought and action (Bourdieu 1977).

In studying individuals' lived experiences with technologies of learning (ToL), Mercer 2022 extends habitus into the digital domain by defining *habitus of technology* as the internalised dispositions and practices that individuals develop specifically in response to their digital interactions (p.48-49). Habitus of technology emerges as a framework "to conceptualise individuals' reflections on their everyday experiences, beliefs, ways of talking about technology and vision for the future potential (of ToL)" (Mercer 2022, p.48). In a related yet distinct

way¹, Romele and Rodighiero 2020 position digital machines, in particular AI algorithms, as “habitus machines” or “habitus producers and reproducers,” in that they not only shape digital practice but individuals’ identity through increased algorithmic curation (p.99). These contemporary reframings capture how technological engagement shapes and reshapes subjectivity itself, embedding new affective, cognitive, and practical orientations toward digital tools.

An AI-specific habitus of technology (or AI-specific habitus, as I will employ the term) extends beyond technical skill; it shapes how users perceive, interpret, and engage with AI across diverse contexts and levels of practice. Crucially, this also implies an ethical dimension²; not only the capacity for deliberate reflection on appropriate use, but also an ingrained set of dispositions that inform action and judgment (Sayer 2005, p.22). In this sense, questions of when and how to use AI, what ethical consequences may follow, and how those consequences shift across different contexts and actors, become *embodied* orientations. These dispositions operate along a continuum from deliberate consideration to unconscious, taken-for-granted tendencies that structure digital practice (Mercer 2022, p.48) As a framework, habitus offers a productive lens for analysing the range and depth of students’ experiences with AI beyond technicalities and beyond the classroom.

Habitus also serves to explain universities’ initial resistance to AI integration and broader institutional reform. As Mercer 2022 observes, “habitus functions as a lag between how it has always been done and how it could be done now” (p.46). This temporal lag embedded within institutional habitus creates a form of structural inertia, wherein universities’ deeply ingrained dispositions toward risk aversion, hierarchical knowledge transmission, and outcome-focused assessment continue to shape responses to emerging technologies, even when such approaches prove inadequate for fostering critical AI engagement (Liu and Bates 2025). Habitus thus reveals how institutional resistance to AI integration reflects the reproduction of educational practices that are fundamentally misaligned with the laboratory-like pedagogies necessary for meaningful student-AI interaction.

¹Romele and Rodighiero 2020 position AI, by virtue of its increasingly personalised algorithmic curation, as a reinforcer of the existing symbolic order through entrenching existing generalisations within social groups (p.109). A phenomenon they call “personalisation without personality.”

²Although Bourdieu never explicitly described moral or ethical dispositions as components of habitus, his definition of dispositions as systems that orient perception, thought, and action leaves space for such an interpretation. Subsequent scholars have extended the concept in this direction. I.e., Sayer 2005 argues that habitus is suffused with moral judgments about what is considered right, fair, or worthy in regards to one’s class.

2.2 The Four Pillar Framework

³ In *Teaching The Unknown* (available in this volume) Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025 propose a pedagogical framework that responds directly to the challenge of teaching with and about AI that resists traditional educational approaches. Rather than attempting to impose conventional teaching methods onto AI contexts, their framework intentionally develops a classroom culture that embraces technological uncertainty as pedagogy, where students can develop critical AI literacy through productive failure and collaborative experimentation.

The framework comprises four pillars that address the unique challenges of AI education. 1) Risk-Embracing Assessment Structures fundamentally reconceptualise evaluation by decoupling task success from assessment outcomes, prioritising students' capacity for critical reflection on their technological interactions over the quality of AI outputs (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025, pp.11-12). 2) Navigating Technological Uncertainty positions uncertainty as an essential pedagogical dimension, creating bounded experimental spaces where students can safely encounter AI's failure modes and develop granular understanding of when, how, and why to employ specific AI tools (pp.12-15). 3) Intentional Classroom Culture Development emphasises psychological safety through systematic rituals and positions educator vulnerability as a deliberate pedagogical strategy (pp.15-17). 4) Facilitating Transformative Learning applies Transformative Learning Theory to structure experiences that catalyse perspective transformation through disorienting dilemmas, critical reflection, and shared discussions (pp.17-18).

Together, these four pillars guide students from possessing an "external AI-LOC" (viewing AI systems as having inherent agency and authority) to an "internal AI-LOC" (perceiving themselves as possessing primary agency in human-AI interaction) (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025, p.4). This progression requires what the authors describe as "substantial time, psychological safety, and structured learning experiences currently absent from most educational contexts" (p.4). Their framework provides a systematic approach to creating laboratory-like learning cultures that can facilitate shifts in students' AI-specific habitus —transforming them from passive, dependent and/or apprehensive consumers to critical users who can evaluate AI capabilities and limitations, reflect on ethical implications, and make deliberate choices about how and when to use AI. By framing these shifts as habitus-level change, their permanence and transferability beyond the classroom and across emerging models is recognised.

³The Politics and International Relations stream of the ARTS3500 capstone unit at Macquarie University in 2024 served as both the experimental classroom from where Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington's four-pillar framework emerged and the ethnographic field site where student transformations were documented.

2.3 The Seminar as Laboratory

During my fieldwork, I often found myself describing the seminar’s distinctive pedagogy as ‘laboratory-like’, a metaphor that gained theoretical depth as I recognised its resonance with Latour and Woolgar’s ethnographic studies of scientific laboratories⁴. As a then-student myself, the laboratory metaphor proved useful for distinguishing the seminar from other conventional university classrooms I had attended at university, where knowledge transmission mainly focused on content delivery from professor to students, and epistemic processes were guided towards achieving predictable outcomes. In the seminar’s laboratory-like environment, students and educators collectively experimented with AI models, testing prompts and interrogating outputs without predetermined answers.

The constant updating of AI models dissolved the usual epistemic hierarchy between teacher and students. It was common in the seminar to arrive in class and discover that the model we had been using in previous weeks had been repurposed overnight. In these situations, we would find ourselves exploring a model’s new capabilities and limitations together with our teacher in real time. The technological uncertainty that makes AI so unsettling became generative here, something to ‘probe’. Failure became data rather than disappointment⁵. In a context where task success was decoupled from outcomes, students took risks with their prompts, reflected openly on unexpected outputs, and embraced the role of active ‘scientists’ in a ‘laboratory.’

With AI readily accessible to most students⁶, laboratory-like pedagogies take on added value. Students can succeed by outsourcing critical thinking to AI, which processes and repackages course material on their behalf. This ease of deferral undermines opportunities for genuine intellectual struggle, making it harder to sustain epistemic engagement in traditional content-focused classrooms (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025, p.4). The problem, then, is not the mode of content delivery itself—since students who resist this deferral must engage critically with the material to achieve satisfactory or higher grades—but rather the reliance on outcome-based assessments, which cannot distinguish between work produced by students and that generated by AI (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025, p.3). What is needed, therefore, is a shift from grading the final product of learning to assessing the quality of students’ engagement with the learning process (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025, p.4).

In the seminar, we engaged with AI systems in two ways (although the

⁴*Laboratory Life* (Latour and Woolgar 1986) positioned laboratories not as neutral spaces for discovering pre-existing facts, but as sites where knowledge is actively constructed through the entanglement of human actors, technological instruments, and social practices. The seminar functioned similarly: rather than transmitting established knowledge about AI, we collectively constructed understanding through experimentation and reflection.

⁵Productive failure becomes a valuable pedagogical strategy when ‘failure’ is contextualised appropriately (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025, p.2).

⁶Ensuring equal and fair access to AI across demographics and geographies remains a critical challenge (Gillespie et al. 2025). See Liu and Bates 2025, pp.19-21 for a discussion of AI access in education.

boundary between both would often blur). On one hand, we approached AI as epistemic partners or resources (AI as a *way* of knowing). For example, in one of the seminar’s signature assessments, we assumed the role of ministers in a 1947 US cabinet simulation⁷. The task was to leverage the capabilities of a chosen AI model to generate context-specific political discourses in favour of either assisting or withdrawing support from Greece in their fight against communism. Our second approach to AI was as an epistemic object of inquiry (AI as *thing* to know). In the weeks that followed the simulation, we interrogated the outputs we produced during the assignment for historical accuracy and ideological assumptions, scanning them for bias and confabulation and reflecting on potential ethical ramifications.

I chose to retain the ‘laboratory’ metaphor throughout this study because it captures something essential about the seminar’s experimental pedagogy that “classroom” simply cannot convey. ‘Laboratory-like’ is employed henceforward as a useful shorthand for the theoretically-dense four pillar framework, offering a more intuitive way to understand this unique learning microculture.

2.4 Positioning the Study within AI Ethnography

To date, ethnographies of AI have largely focused on communities of developers and professional users (Seaver 2018; Govia 2020; Richardson 2015). Even after generative AI systems like ChatGPT became publicly available, minimal ethnographic attention has been paid to non-expert users such as students. In the domain of education, the few available ethnographies have predominantly explored pedagogical research and educators’ experiences (see Panke 2025; Molek 2023), leaving a notable gap in our understanding of student-AI interactions. This absence is especially striking given that university students occupy a central position in quantitative analyses, exhibiting concerning (yet varied) patterns of AI use (Gillespie et al. 2025).

My research seeks to address this gap and contribute to the growing field of AI ethnography by investigating the overarching question: *How does the intentional design of AI learning ‘laboratories’ transform students’ AI-specific ‘habitus’ while demonstrating possibilities for sector-wide change in higher education?*

3 Methodology

3.1 Rationale: Why Ethnography for AI?

Recent years have witnessed growing calls for the use of ethnography in studying AI (Voorst and Ahlin 2024; Mercer 2022; Raffaetà, Santanera, and Esposito 2023). While large-scale quantitative studies, such as Gillespie et al. 2025 advance our understanding of student uses and attitudes towards AI, statistical

⁷Simulation overview available at Council on Foreign Relations 2021

approaches are limited in their ability to capture the broader cultural and educational contexts within which AI technologies are embedded. For example, Seaver 2018 raises concerns over purely quantitative analyses and their failure to capture the deeper power dynamics and structural conditions shaping automated systems' and their outcomes. Similarly, Voorst and Ahlin 2024 caution against neglecting the contextual factors underlying the generalisations represented in quantitative studies on AI. Context-blind approaches risk flattening key nuances in how the public engages with automated algorithms, reinforcing the perception of AI as autonomous and unknowable 'black boxes'—a view that fosters either overreliance or unwarranted scepticism (Voorst and Ahlin 2024). In higher education, a lack of contextual awareness may help explain why universities initially framed AI use purely through the lens of academic misconduct. Without an understanding of the cultural factors driving students' widespread adoption of AI, their responses relied on decontextualised (albeit concerning) statistics rather than the underlying conditions shaping student behaviour.

Liu and Bates 2025 highlight culture as both "the deepest challenge and greatest opportunity" for successfully integrating AI into higher education (p.6). Their CRAFT framework positions culture as the foundation upon which the other key factors (Rules, Access, Familiarity, and Trust) might thrive or dwindle. The authors define culture as the shared "attitudes, philosophies, and perspectives" across individuals, academic institutions, and governments (Liu and Bates 2025, p.14). Without attention to cultural contexts, collaboration and critical engagement with AI is expected to suffer, undermining long-term planning (Liu and Bates 2025, p.37). Over time, this can erode trust between students, educators, and their institutions, trust in AI itself, and the motivation to develop or sustain familiarity with emerging tools (Liu and Bates 2025, p.37). In this sense, neglecting the role of culture in fostering critical, sector-wide engagement with AI represents an opportunity cost for universities. Initial findings from research beyond the CRAFT framework show that traditional content-based classrooms can be re-designed to foster critical student engagement with AI and with students' own epistemic processes, supporting more meaningful learning experiences and broader, institutional transformation from the bottom-up (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025; Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025).

Anthropology's distinctive method of participant observation offers a way to generate rich qualitative insights that ground the patterns represented in quantitative research (Voorst and Ahlin 2024; Seaver 2018). Ethnography allows researchers to situate AI engagement within wider institutional cultures, pedagogical practices, and value systems that shape students' uses and attitudes towards emerging technologies. Thus, ethnographic insights can be beneficial for creatively addressing not just students' uncritical use of AI, but the broader cultural landscape that shapes it. In developing avenues for exploring algorithms as culture, Seaver 2018 inquired about the ways in which algorithms materialise values and cultural meanings. Motivated by this query, my research asks: *what cultural logics underlie students' uses and misuses of AI? and how might these logics be reworked through bottom-up, post-transactional pedagogical approaches?* This study aligns with emerging scholarship arguing that students' complacent

engagement with AI reflects not simply algorithmic affordances, but broader institutional logics at work within the university itself (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025). More precisely, transactional educational models — with their emphasis on credentialism, top-down content delivery, and predefined outcomes over processes— incentivise forms of using AI that favour expediency over critical engagement, by fostering risk-averse learning environments that sideline experimentation and genuine inquiry (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025).

In alignment with the broader argument supported by fellow contributors to this volume; I argue that critical student engagement with AI is inseparable from sector-wide transformation. In *The Emperor’s New Clothes: A Manifesto for Universities in an AI-Hunted World* (available in this volume) Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025 envision post-transactional universities as dynamic institutions that prioritise process over outcomes, real-world impact over credentials, and learning as an adaptive, capability-driven journey, where experimentation and productive failure is embraced as pedagogy. Findings from this study show that when these pedagogical principles are embraced, they cultivate laboratory-like classroom cultures where students not only build critical AI literacy, but also reclaim learning as a meaningful, transformative practice, countering the growing tendency (amplified by AI) to approach education merely as a transactional means to an end.

3.2 Emergent Research Design in a Rapidly Evolving Field

In contrast to methods that define variables and hypotheses in advance, ethnography embraces open-ended inquiry, allowing for unanticipated discoveries through in-depth interviews, participant observation, and close engagement with the everyday realities of human-machine interaction (Voorst and Ahlin 2024). This open-endedness is particularly valuable in the context of AI, a rapidly developing and highly unstable technology whose capabilities, limitations, and social implications are continually shifting as algorithms are updated and repurposed. Rather than seeking fixed causal explanations, ethnography is equipped to capture the emergent, contingent, and situated nature of AI’s integration into (but not limited to) education, offering a methodological flexibility that aligns with the technological indeterminacy at the heart of AI systems.

At the outset, the focus of my research was on documenting how students’ uses and perceptions of AI changed during the seminar. Yet, as new models and capabilities were released in real time over the course of my fieldwork, my participants’ engagements with AI deepened, giving rise to new ethical reflections that exceeded my initial scope. Discussions naturally expanded to questions about the role of the humanities in an AI-saturated future, and the uncertain fate of work, politics and education in light of increasingly capable generative technologies. Because my research was not bound by predefined hypotheses, I was able to broaden the inquiry and trace the emergence of these changing ethical dispositions. In the findings section, I emphasise the seminar’s distinctive pedagogy in encouraging unscripted, student-led discussions on AI ethics and on what Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025 term an ‘AI-haunted world.’ and

what that might look like.

I discovered my research site unexpectedly, when I enrolled in my university's first offering of an introductory seminar on generative AI. In the first two weeks of the course I noticed how my classmates' perceptions and attitudes towards AI changed as we learnt how to operate a class of generative AI called Large Language Models⁸ (LLMs). What began as a weary first attempt at demystifying AI soon transformed into an ethnographic opportunity. Like most, I joined with an apprehensive attitude towards AI and virtually no knowledge on how these tools worked. But I was curious.

When I settled on the decision to conduct this ethnography, I disclosed my research intentions to my classmates and requested their permission to document our shared experiences. Informed consent was obtained verbally at the outset of the research and reiterated prior to each interview. To protect participant confidentiality, all names used in this study are pseudonyms. This project was undertaken as part of *ANTH3024: Doing Ethnography*, a final-year unit on ethnographic research methods at Macquarie University. Student research for this unit is covered by approval from the Human Research Ethics Low Risk Committee at Macquarie University. As part of that framework, students are provided with ethics materials to adapt for their projects; I used these to secure participant consent and ensure confidentiality and anonymity throughout my study.

My dual position as both fellow student and researcher offered a unique vantage point from which to observe and participate in students' early encounters with LLMs. As preliminary blueprints for integrating AI into tertiary education emerge, growing attention is being paid to students' epistemic standpoints, reflected in calls for stronger partnerships between students and institutions in the design of curricula. In their whitepaper for AI integration into higher education, Liu and Bates 2025 outline student partnerships as one of two key priorities for sector-wide action; "the elevation of students as partners through (...) co-design of learning experiences, direct input into assessment redesign, and collaborative resource development" (p.7). In this context, my epistemic standpoint as an undergraduate arts student then enrolled at Macquarie University positioned me within the lived experiences under study, endowing my ethnographic observations with an insider's sensitivity to students' transformations and Macquarie's institutional and social culture. Standpoint epistemology holds that the knower's social position is not only inseparable from their knowledge production, but also a valuable source of insight, especially when investigating structures and experiences to which they are directly subject (Kukla 2021).

⁸In simple terms, LLMs are 'smart' computer programs, or neural networks, trained on vast text corpora to understand and generate human-like text. LLMs learn by predicting the next word in text sequences, developing sophisticated language understanding and generation abilities through exposure to diverse datasets including web content, books, and code (Burtell and Toner 2024). Modern LLMs excel at text comprehension, question answering and reasoning tasks. Yet, they face significant challenges including hallucination issues where they generate convincing but factually incorrect information. They lack true contextual understanding and operate as sophisticated pattern-matching systems rather than genuine comprehension engines.

Likewise, the situated experiences of my fellow student participants constitute equally significant epistemic resources that offer insights into how educational cultures foster or constrain critical engagement with AI. In seeking to retain the specificity of these perspectives, I have foregrounded participants' voices throughout the analysis, allowing their narratives to inform and shape the interpretation.

3.3 Research Setting and Participant Overview

My research involved a cohort of 11 Politics and International Relations (POIR) students participating in a semester-long seminar on Large Language Models (LLMs) at Macquarie University in Sydney. Students had been given the opportunity to enrol in one of three discipline specific streams in place of the regular arts capstone unit: History, Philosophy, or Politics and International Relations. The two-hour weekly seminar taught students how to use and critique LLMs in relation to various POIR topics.

The participants were all between the ages of 19-23, with the exception of one student who was 40. All of the group had limited to no understanding of how LLMs operated before enrolling in the seminar, yet all had previously experimented with free, mainstream models such as ChatGPT⁹ to varying degrees.

3.4 Data Gathering Design

Following Voorst and Ahlin 2024 methodological framework for AI ethnography, which emphasises committed fieldwork, trust-building, and attention to subtle data, I implemented a multi-sited approach to data collection. My approach combined traditional participant observation with digital ethnographic methods across three settings over 12 weeks. The main site was the weekly two-hour in-person seminar, where I documented nuances and changes in students' behaviours through their participation in class discussions and AI-assisted group assignments.

To balance the lack of observable activity when students operated LLMs beyond the classroom, I extended my participant observation to two digital spaces. The first was the official Teams class chat, moderated by the unit convenor. The second, an informal student-led Instagram group chat, emerged as a particularly rich source of ethnographic insight. This unmoderated space became a virtual forum where students exchanged tips and advice on how to operate AI, recounted successes and failures, voiced hopes and concerns, and shared AI-related memes.

To complement the above, I conducted open-ended, semi-structured interviews with seven participants at various points throughout the semester. These interviews proved invaluable in uncovering aspects of AI engagement that I could not readily access through participant observation, though they presented their

⁹Available versions of Open AI ChatGPTs up until that time (August 2024) included GPT-4o mini and prior models.

own methodological challenges. The data I collected was reliant on my participants' memory recalling their past interactions, feelings and attitudes around AI, and the inherent limitations of interview data based on my participant's self-awareness, the question I chose (and did not choose) to ask, and my interpretation of their responses.

4 Findings

'Zoe talks of her experience prompting Claude to help her write our upcoming assignment for this seminar. She is confident in her tone, she uses technical jargon, she has critical insights of the limitations of this model for writing. Again, I am reminded of how much her habitus of technology has transformed since day one.'

4 September 2024 - Excerpt from my field notes.

As the seminar progressed, it became clear that students were developing sophisticated technical skills: learning to intentionally select models and craft effective prompts to achieve desired outcomes, and critically evaluate outputs for errors, bias, and usability. Yet, what stood out to me were the ways in which student's perceptions, attitudes, and reflections radically shifted as they collectively learned how to critically operate LLMs in an experimental, safe-to-fail space. In other words, I became increasingly interested in the subjective dimension of students' AI use, beyond technicalities. As my fieldwork advanced, I witnessed how student's engagement with AI was not limited to the physical confines of the seminar room, but rather, permeated student's everyday lives, reshaping their ongoing relationships with AI; their careers; and ethical dispositions towards these technologies. These deeper, pervasive shifts that accompanied the acquisition of technical skills led me to conceptualise students' experiences as shifts in their AI-specific habitus.

The experience of Zoe, one of my key participants, illustrates the analytical value of habitus, capturing how technological practice is deeply entangled with students' subjectivities and, in turn, shaped by the cultural contexts in which these emerging technologies are embedded (Costa, Hammond, and Younie 2019, p.397). On the first day of the seminar, Zoe's silence was palpable as our teacher introduced LLMs and exemplified operations on the projected screen. When I interviewed Zoe early in the semester, she reflected back on that moment: "(I felt) *Completely overwhelmed, I felt like he (our teacher) was talking another language*". Encouraged by her response, I shared with Zoe that the public tends to perceive AI as a "black box" (Voorst and Ahlin 2024). Her response was immediate and revealing: "*That's what it feels like! It feels like I haven't quite been authorised to get it *laughs*. It feels like I'm an imposter using the AI*". Zoe's use of the word 'imposter' immediately stood out to me.

Zoe's testimony offers a window into the assumptions and experiences that students bring to their first encounters with AI in educational settings. Consider her choice of words. On the surface, Zoe's self description as an "imposter"

and “unauthorised” AI user reflect her insecurities and sense of illegitimacy as a student consumer. At a deeper level, her testimony subtly reflects the educational culture around AI. It nods to the consequences of universities’ failure to provide clear guidelines for AI use and their framing of AI engagement exclusively through the lens of academic misconduct. This cultural positioning hinders meaningful engagement by fostering the very attitudes represented in large-scale analyses: students either concealing their use of AI to complete assignments or remaining reluctant to experiment with tools that have been institutionally constructed as instruments of academic dishonesty (Gillespie et al. 2025, p.90).

Anthropologist of technology Nick Seaver asks: “What local practices of analogy, valuation, and contextualisation can we find when we recognise that algorithms, in spite of it all, are thoroughly dependent on human sense-making?” (Seaver 2018). By attending to students’ situated experiences, we can better understand the social influences and cultural logics that shape their relationships with AI, and re-work them to cultivate dispositions that favour critical engagement. In our first interview, I asked Zoe how she had felt about AI before the seminar. She responded: “*I was kind of overwhelmed, because I always felt very stupid. I couldn’t understand (...) everyone around me in my family was very threatened by AI, that it would take over jobs (...) I kinda held similar views, especially when you go to the (supermarket) checkout and it’s all machines that are doing things for you.*” Zoe’s account illustrates how broader social anxieties about technological change become encoded into personal understandings. In her case, institutional framings (AI as plagiarism) and family narratives (automation as a threat) together compounded Zoe’s self-perceived inadequacy (“*I’m an imposter using the AI*”).

‘When we arrived in class, we were surprised when our teacher asked us to arrange our chairs into a wide circle to reflect on our processes to date. Motivated by the refreshing activity and the novelty of arranging the classroom space thus, we began our class discussion by sharing our motivations for joining the seminar. Students went around describing having felt intimidated, scared, or unsettled by AI prior to discovering how LLMs actually worked, though also curious and amazed at its potential. Almost everyone mentioned an interest in examining the ethical implications of AI across different domains (work, education, politics, media) and each participant connected these motivations to personal experiences where they had seen AI influence their work, studies, or current affairs. The motivation to learn AI out of fear of being “left behind” or made redundant in the future of work was a common theme in student’s contributions.’

7 August 2024 - Excerpt from my field notes.

By bringing culture back into the picture, we can uncover, as Seaver 2018 proposes, the culturally-situated processes that shape how students and institutions make sense of AI, and consequently how they engage with it. If our

goal is to integrate AI into universities in ways that enhance rather than erode education, re-working current student and institutional dispositions towards AI is essential. Habitus shapes culture, just as culture continually reshapes habitus (Bourdieu 1977). In the same way, student habituses and institutional culture, as exemplified in Zoe’s testimonies, are mutually reinforcing. Outlining what characterises students’ AI habituses prior to seminar enrollment is a crucial first step in pinpointing the constraints that must be reworked at both institutional and individual levels. As Mercer 2022 explains; “Identifying the constraints that form the Habitus of Technology provides the ability to undo the influence of the dispositions and dependencies in the present” (p.181). The contours of students’ AI-specific habitus prior to enrolling in the seminar begin to emerge in shared, impromptu discussions like the one described above, where students reflect on their past perceptions of AI, their motivations for joining the seminar, and the ways their assumptions have shifted as their AI literacy develops.

Thanks to the psychological safety nurtured in the seminar, class discussions were one of my key entry points into students’ past experiences with AI. The openness with which students reflected allowed me to outline general patterns in students’ pre-seminar AI-specific habituses and document changes as the semester progressed. In fact, whilst conducting this study I found that students are not only willing, but eager to recount past and current AI-related behaviours and beliefs within classrooms that take the time and resources to cultivate the trust, belonging and psychological safety necessary for interpersonal risk-taking, such as openly sharing, as many of my participants did, having used AI in ways that are considered academically punishable¹⁰. (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025, p.11).

‘Our teacher asked whether (and if so, in which ways) we relied on AI to get through our degrees. He assured us that our contributions would remain confidential and were meant only to help him understand our experiences; we wouldn’t be penalised for admitting to using AI in our studies. Encouraged, students went around openly sharing their experiences. Most acknowledged having used AI in their studies at some point; for assignments, preparing for tutorials, or studying for exams. Many attributed this to time pressures, especially those who balanced work with study. A recurring theme was the feeling that using AI was a pragmatic response to these pressures. Many agreed that they would rather turn to AI for help than fail an assignment, turn up unprepared for a class, or, even worse, failing a unit, which not only meant falling behind or yet another financial burden, but a stain in students academic transcripts; a massive cost for arts students in an increasingly reduced, and thus competitive, job market.’

¹⁰Students’ eagerness to participate in discussions on AI use within universities underscores their potential as valuable partners for informing the integration of AI in higher education (For recommendations on how institutions may partner with students, see Liu and Bates 2025, pp.39-40).

4 September 2024 - Excerpt from my field notes.

Students' AI-specific habituses prior to seminar enrollment are characteristically uninformed. After repeated reviews of my notes, interview recordings, and transcripts I can confirm that not a single student expressed nor exhibited confidence in their understanding of how AI systems worked before the seminar¹¹. From this generalised lack of knowledge, student habituses encompassed a combination of the following dispositions: apprehension, distrust, dependence, curiosity, and even fear. Attributing these mostly unfavourable dispositions to student deficiencies would be a simplification. To a large extent, they emerge as logical outcomes of the broader social and educational cultures in which students are situated. Academic dishonesty is often attributed to personal failings such as poor time management or procrastination, yet within transactional educational models, the turn to AI also represents one amongst many "rational responses to a system that rewards credential acquisition over learning" (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025, p.2). For this particular group of arts students, AI assistance becomes especially appealing when faced with the prospect of a competitive job market that is particularly unforgiving to humanities graduates. Within such a credential-driven landscape, the view amongst many of my participants (most of whom were undertaking their last semester at university) was that a single blemish on an academic transcript can function as a decisive 'one-strike-and-you're-out'.

This argument is not intended to excuse or dismiss plagiarism; rather, it highlights the cultural logics that underpin AI-enabled academic misuse, which is in itself a symptom of the limitations of current educational approaches that long predate the release of GenAI to the public (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025, p.2). More importantly, it underscores this pressing question:

"What would universities look like if student work created real value beyond grades? This question grows urgent as AI handles routine cognitive tasks. If universities continue producing graduates trained for work AI already performs better, a significant part of what they offer students evaporates" (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025, p.5).

Students' pre-seminar habituses were also characterised by a generalised tendency to treat AI systems as endowed with inherent agency and authority, what Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025 call an external AI Locus of Control (p.4). This disposition drives students to defer to AI rather than direct it. Mid semester, I sat with Alfred in the courtyard outside Macquarie's Art Faculty for our interview. Consider his account of students' perceptions on AI.

Me: *How did you feel about AI before we started the seminar? What was your perception of it?*

Alfred: *In terms of emotion it wasn't fear, but it was definitely apprehensiveness, and a fear of the unknown, because I didn't have*

¹¹See 'Methodological enactments' in Seaver 2017 for the processes through which the public (and oftentimes, AI developers themselves) come to understand algorithms as 'black boxes.'

knowledge about the ability of AI and I was going off what was being fed to me by the mass media and I was viewing it as this inherent threat.

Me: *Has your understanding of LLMs and AI changed at all since we started the seminar?*

Alfred: *(...)In journalism class, there was such intense fear of AI and also viewing it as something that is extractive. The class used technical terms that were inaccurate, and technical terms that I didn't know existed before the class. My understanding now is much more well rounded.*

I encouraged Alfred to tell me a bit more about this situation that unfolded in journalism class;

Alfred: *It was them referencing AI as like a living conscious, thinking, breathing thing...*

Me: *How did that make you feel? That your classmates were referring to AI like a living thing?*

Alfred: *I was somewhat appalled because I knew it was inaccurate and didn't have a brain and it was relying on human programming. And its capacities are based on human capacities so, humankind, we're the inventors, we developed it, so as long as we adequately regulate it, don't do something really stupid, I feel like we'll always have superiority over AI, but in that unit, it was totally flipped over its head, and it was viewed as if AI had control over us, and AI is making decisions for us, and I view that as very outlandish and not true.*

Me: *If you hadn't attended this seminar, do you think you would have perhaps shared these views?*

Alfred: *Yeah I think so, for sure, I would have been a lot more passive. Unfortunately we gravitate to what we know and those are forms of mass media, and their outwards projections of AI is contradictory (...). I feel, this whole seminar has mythbusted norms that are inaccurate for me, and I find that very useful as a citizen in a digital age, now I have an understanding of AI, its capabilities, implications, and accurate practices.*

Alfred's perspective provides a window into the culture of AI in university life, where AI is perceived as posing "an inherent threat" and "has control over us", a sentiment that, as the reader may recall, closely mirrors Zoe's and her family's. Alfred's testimony on the views held by fellow students reveals that fear, distrust, and an external AI locus of control were not merely coincidental dispositions among seminar participants, but rather widespread attitudes among university students generally—a perspective that Alfred attributes to lack of knowledge and inaccurate media portrayals.

Through Liu and Bates 2025 CRAFT framework, the current higher education landscape reveals a concerning pattern of interconnected failures that actively undermine productive and responsible AI integration. ‘Culture’ remains trapped in what Liu and Bates identify as ”piecemeal and reactive approaches focusing on immediate concerns like academic integrity rather than systematic integration” (Liu and Bates 2025, p.6). ‘Rules’ continue to fall behind as AI use becomes increasingly more widespread amongst students and AI’s capabilities are continuously updated (p.17). Meanwhile, ‘Access’ inequities are exacerbated by institutional framings of AI as plagiarism, which disincentivise some students from exploring AI tools that could support and enhance their learning out of fear of academic misconduct, while others continue to use these tools without regulation, risking academic violations and creating an uneven playing field. As clearly evidenced in my participants’ first encounters with LLMs in the early days of the seminar and their reflections on past use, ‘Familiarity’ remains critically underdeveloped as ”universities are not providing the necessary familiarity-building activities that students need” and students continue to use AI tools in their studies nonetheless¹²(p.22).

However, these patterns are not immutable. As Sayer 2005 emphasises: “experiences can modify the habitus and produce new dispositions, and skills, enabling people to react in new ways.” (p.25). The learning microculture created within the seminar provides evidence that re-designing classrooms as laboratories can facilitate profound shifts in students’ AI-specific habituses that support critical use. This progression requires what Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025 describe as ”substantial time, psychological safety, and structured learning experiences currently absent from most educational contexts” (p.4). In the final section of this study’s findings, I discuss changes in students’ AI specific habituses in the ways they differ from their pre-seminar habituses, with particular attention to the role of ethical reflexivity in students’ AI engagement.

‘Zoe talks of her experience prompting Claude to help her write our upcoming assignment for this seminar. She is confident in her tone, she uses technical jargon, she has critical insights of the limitations of this model for writing. Again, I am reminded of how much her habitus of technology has transformed since day one.’

4 September 2024 - Excerpt from my field notes.

By semester’s end, Zoe’s transformation was remarkable. The above excerpt from my fieldnotes stands in sharp contrast to her initial confusion and perceived level of competency. Her contributions to the class not only demonstrated technical proficiency, but also critical awareness. She explains: ”When i was able to program the system prompt to fit my unit guidelines for another unit just so I could ask it general questions and get it to extract sections of legislations, that was like, wow, this could be super helpful, (...) it made me understand, ok, this

¹²Macquarie University’s experimental seminar constitutes a commendable initiative for developing familiarity.

is a tool to help me, it's not my enemy, and it's not entirely stupid, and this could be extremely helpful for the future".

Zoe's journey from feeling like an 'imposter' to confidently discussing her use of LLMs demonstrates the seminar's pedagogy success. Over the course of the seminar, all participants moved from expressing limited knowledge and confidence about how AI works to developing sophisticated technical skills for operating LLMs. Their competencies included deliberately selecting models, intentionally crafting prompts to achieve desired outcomes, and critically scanning outputs for bias, error, and confabulation. Yet, changes in students' dispositions and ways of thinking about AI suggest a deeper transformation that went beyond technical proficiency. By framing these shifts at the level of habitus, I point to the durability and transferability of these critical dispositions beyond the classroom and across emerging models.

The transformation from pre seminar AI-specific habituses that are uninformed, and/or dependent, fearful, and non-transparent into habituses that favoured critical, responsible, and transparent use of AI involved the formation of an ethical AI conscience amongst students; an awareness of what constitutes ethical use and misuse of AI and the potential ramifications of uninformed or uncontrolled applications in different contexts. In *The Moral Significance of Class*, Sayer 2005 broadens Bourdieu's habitus to accommodate "lay reflexivity as an influence upon (...) behaviour" (p.18). Dispositions of the habitus are suffused with moral judgment, Sayer 2005 argues, habitus shapes what people see as right, wrong, fair, or unfair (p.19). Thus, habitus encompasses a moral dimension¹³ — both an ingrained set of embodied orientations that inform ethical action and the capacity for deliberate, ongoing ethical decision-making (Sayer 2005, p.19). This latter form of "lay reflexivity," as Sayer 2005 calls it, becomes essential with AI's technological uncertainty, whereby models' capabilities and limitations are constantly changing. In this context, questions of when and how to use AI, what ethical consequences may follow, and how those consequences shift across different contexts and actors must be deliberately re-considered in tandem with technological developments.

'Isabella, Molly and Zoe recount carrying out an "experiment" outside the classroom to test whether LLMs are fatphobic.

Zoe: "(...) And of course it was fatphobic" Isabella: "Yes, but we wanted to know how far it would go" Zoe: "But there are no limits" Molly: "No, yes there are limits, look! Listen!"

Molly reads out their prompt and methodically explains how they tested the AI's responses for fatphobic bias. The class erupts in knowing laughter at their findings, but this quickly transitions into a more serious discussion. Students go around sharing their thoughts

¹³Although Bourdieu never explicitly described moral or ethical dispositions as components of habitus, his definition of dispositions as systems that orient perception, thought, and action leaves space for such an interpretation. Subsequent scholars have extended the concept in this direction: Sayer 2005 argues that habitus is suffused with moral judgments about what is considered right, fair, or worthy in regards to one's class.

and the rest murmur in agreement as they reflect on the implications. Several voices echo "this is dangerous" and "this is scary." What began as an informal experiment clearly struck a chord.'

2 October 2024 - Excerpt from my field notes.

Much of our weekly seminar time was devoted to exploring the ethics of AI, with students regularly voicing their experiences, concerns, and ethical judgments in peer-led exchanges. These discussions frequently emerged spontaneously, spilling over from formal class debates into informal spaces such as our Instagram group chat and casual conversations before and after class. Through this ongoing discourse, the role of the seminar in facilitating a collective process of ethical meaning-making became evident. Students collaboratively negotiated, and at times revised, their stances on how AI should and should not be used.

The "fatphobic-AI experiment," as the student trio above called it, demonstrates how inquiry into AI's ethical dimensions extended beyond the classroom and formal assessments. In such instances, the value of decoupling grades from mere task success becomes clear: when success is not tied to assessment outcomes, students feel empowered to explore (Balloun-Stanton and Torrington 2025, p.11). For Molly, Isabella, and Zoe, this freedom catalysed an intrinsic motivation to probe and uncover potential ethical risks through their own experiments, rather than simply performing for grades. As Zoe once said to me: "I feel like I've learned a lot just from having the tools to kind of have a fidget with it myself and playing around with it."

In their effort to move beyond the dichotomous view of humans versus algorithms that characterises social research on technology, Raffaetà, Santanera, and Esposito 2023 observe that "data and technology are heavily reconfiguring our daily lives (...) they rely on human choices and practices, being embedded into social relations, cultural contexts, infrastructures and institutions" (p.1). Throughout the semester, students' ethical reflections on AI emerged through their specific social and cultural contexts, often situating their reflections in their lived experiences and professional aspirations. When I asked Molly whether she had encountered any ethical concerns in the semester, she drew upon her experience as a paralegal to ground her response: "*The fact that AI will never say it is wrong, that is quite concerning, when it confabulates, when it might not know the answer but it will tell you something anyway, I think that might be a big problem, if you're not really evaluating what comes out of it if it's telling you complete lies. I think there is a concern that you can use AI without cross checking, and I think of that a lot in the legal setting, cause there's been a couple of cases, and that's quite concerning*". Another participant, Zeke, traced quite a different personal connection; drawing from his experience as a high school teacher, Zeke expressed growing concern about detecting ChatGPT use in his students' homework. Julie, whose studies in politics and international relations informed her perspective, raised critical questions about the implications of automated military equipment; while Nikhil brought attention to the often-overlooked environmental toll of sustaining AI technologies. These find-

ings gain particular salience against the backdrop of higher education’s growing disconnect between coursework and real-world relevance (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025, p.5). My participants’ narratives demonstrate that when provided with appropriate pedagogical structures, students naturally bridge this divide through exploring and reflecting on their newly acquired technical skills not as isolated academic exercises, but as capacities that meaningfully connect to their professional trajectories, career aspirations, and lived experiences beyond the university.

When I interviewed Molly a few weeks before the semester’s end, her ethical awareness often seeped into our conversation: *”I’m positive about AI, yeah, I think there are risks and I think they need to be duly addressed, but I think the media tends to make it more scary than it is. This class has actually been reassuring that AI is way more stupid than people think it is”*. Crucially, the seminar did not prescribe or conform to any external, predetermined ethical guidelines for AI use. Instead, its pedagogical design honored the initial offering made to students: “We will be exploring questions of AI-safety, AI-bias, and the problematic issues of AI and representation (...)” This exploratory framework empowered students with genuine agency to experiment, debate, and develop their own ethical positions through collaborative inquiry.

The transition from possessing an external AI Locus to Control to an internal AI LOC (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025, p.4) amongst students in the seminar offers an important counterpoint to what Seaver 2018 identifies as a prevalent tendency to treat AI systems as autonomous agents, divorced from human culture and practice. While many industries and governments advocate for ethical guidelines to be embedded within algorithms themselves, social researchers emphasise the need to re-incorporate human agency into the picture. Seaver 2018 cautions: “If we grant algorithms autonomy, treating them as though they are external to human culture, then we cannot make any sense of this story” (2018). In the context of education, I contend that when institutions frame AI primarily as a threat to be regulated rather than a tool requiring student agency, we effectively absolve students of the responsibility to develop the reflexive capabilities essential for AI engagement that supports, rather than sabotages, their educational development. As students’ technical skills developed, our teacher consistently reminded us: “own your output”. The meaning of Professor Stanton-Ballsun’s instruction (and its caution) only became clear to us later in the semester: learn to be in control of what you input into these models, and you will increase your control over what comes out. His diagnostic question became a touchstone for our practice: “Can you confidently claim to own what you’ve produced with AI’s help?” If the answer is no, he warned, you are likely letting AI do the work for you.

My observations indicate that when students are provided with the necessary tools, activities, flexibility and guidance to investigate, discuss, and reflect on AI ethics, they harness agency in forming ethical roadmaps meaningful to their contexts. This epistemic autonomy stands in contrast to dominant educational approaches characterised by the delivery of content and standardisation of outcomes. The seminar underscores the necessity of reimagining AI pedagogy:

replacing current models with ones that prioritise inquiry, experimentation, and reflective agency. As consistently argued, in doing so students did not merely acquire technical skills isolated from world-making—they reclaimed ownership over their epistemic processes, enabling them to derive authentic value from learning.

5 Conclusion

“Our degrees are going to have so much more value in the future, even with the growth of AI, because we are the humanities, we are the people, and AI is not human, it will never be able to do what we do.”

- Molly.

As I sat in the seminar room that final day, listening to Molly articulate what we had collectively discovered about the irreplaceable value of human insight, I was struck by how far we had travelled not just as students learning about AI, but as humans grappling with what it means to retain critical thinking and agency in an increasingly automated world. This ethnographic study began with an observation of how students’ perceptions and attitudes towards AI changed during an experimental seminar. What emerged through four months of fieldwork were three interconnected insights that reveal both the cultural roots of current AI challenges in higher education and the potential of leveraging cultural insights in the design of post-transactional classrooms.

The first insight emerged from students’ testimonies about their pre-seminar experiences with AI. Students’ widespread concealment of AI use, their rational responses to time pressures, and their external AI locus-of-control pointed to cultural logics embedded within transactional educational models rather than personal failings. When universities position AI primarily through the lens of academic misconduct without providing familiarity-building opportunities, they foster the apprehension, dependence, and non-transparent use that characterise students’ pre-seminar habituses. The increasingly transactional nature of tertiary education, in which credential acquisition is prioritised over learning, together with systemic pressures and the growing capabilities of AI, creates conditions for student disengagement, performative critical thinking, and reliance on AI (Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025).

The seminar’s implementation of risk-embracing assessment structures, navigation of technological uncertainty, intentional classroom culture development, and facilitation of transformative learning created what students experienced as fundamentally different conditions for engagement (Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025). This laboratory-like environment revealed that when universities embrace technological uncertainty as pedagogy rather than problem, students respond by reclaiming their roles as active investigators. The seminar functioned as a learning microculture where collaborative experimentation and productive

failure replaced traditional top-down teaching methods, re-engaging students in their own epistemic processes.

Students developed ethical AI awareness through collaborative meaning-making rather than prescribed guidelines. The teacher’s consistent reminder to “own your output” became internalised as students learned to direct rather than defer to AI systems. This shift represents a profound transformation extending far beyond technical proficiency to include ethical AI awareness that endured beyond the classroom, enabling students to derive authentic value from learning through acquiring capabilities that are relevant in real-world contexts.

5.1 Implications for Sector-Wide Change

As Molly observed, the value of education lies precisely in developing critical thinking and ethical reflection capabilities that enable productive and responsible engagement with AI systems. The ethnographic evidence presented here supports the view that universities should embrace AI as an opportunity for fundamental reform, rather than resist it in order to preserve existing educational models whose value is already diminishing. (Liu and Bates 2025; Ballsun-Stanton and Khalid 2025).

This study contributes to emerging scholarship positioning culture as central to successful AI integration (Liu and Bates 2025; Ballsun-Stanton and Torrington 2025) while providing qualitative evidence for laboratory-like pedagogies’ effectiveness in fostering critical AI literacy. The findings demonstrate that when educational cultures are redesigned thus, profound transformations in students’ AI-specific habituses that go beyond technical competency to encompass epistemic agency and ethical awareness become possible.

As these technologies continue advancing, perhaps what we need most is not more sophisticated algorithms, but more sophisticated ways of understanding and critically engaging with them. In higher education, bottom-up change aligned with post-transactional pedagogies offers one path forward.

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